

WINGBLADES OF GLASS FIBRE REINFORCED POLYESTER FOR A 630 kW WINDTURBINE DESIGN, FABRICATION AND MATERIALS TESTING

B. S. JOHANSEN, H. LILHOLT and Aa. LYSTRUP

*Metallurgy Department. Risø National Laboratory
DK-4000 Roskilde, Denmark*

Wingblades for a 630 kW windturbine are described. The conceptual design of the 20 m long wingblades comprises a load-bearing spar with aerodynamically shaped shells. The 12 m outer spar is made of highly directional glass fibres in a polyester matrix. The spar is fabricated by a special tape winding technique, which gives a high volume fraction of glass fibres oriented nearly parallel to the spar axis. Materials testing of the spar material and component testing of (sections of) the wingblade verify the properties of the glass-polyester laminate and the design of the wingblade.

INTRODUCTION

A windturbine of nominal power 630 kW has been designed and built by the Danish electricity utilities. The design of the rotor and of the wingblades was carried out with little previous experience in this field, and a certain amount of development work and component testing was necessary during the design phase. The main characteristics of the windturbine (Fig. 1) are listed in Table 1.

Nominal (max.) power	630 kW
Generator, induction	1500 rpm
Tower, conical, reinforced concrete	
Height of hub	45 m
Hub, rigid (non-flapping)	
Rotor, 3 wingblades, upwind of tower	
Rotor diameter	40 m
Wingblade, airfoil	NACA 44 xx
Wingblade, tip speed	70 m/s
Angular velocity, ω	3.5 s ⁻¹
Windspeed, start/max.power/stop	6/13/25 m/s

Table 1

The power of the windturbine is regulated by varying the pitch of the wingblades; the inner 8 m of each wingblade is fixed, while the outer 12 m has variable pitch. The stop position for the wingblades is the stalled position, i.e. the flat side of the blades is facing towards the wind.

DESIGN OF THE WINGBLADES

The three wingblades are composed of an inner wing of length 8 m, and an outer wing of length 12 m. The wingblades are supported by a system of tie-struts between the blades out to radius ca. 8 m. The aerodynamic shape of the wingblades was selected from standard profiles (NACA) with known aerodynamic lift-coefficients, under consideration of energy production and methods for regulation of power during operation.

The profiles are NACA 4412 at the wingtip and NACA 4433 at the root-end (radius 2 m). The twist of the outer wingblade (Fig. 2) is zero at the wing-tip (cord 0.6 m) with linear variation to 7.8° at radius 8 m, (cord 1.8 m). On the basis of the statistical wind distribution and a nominal life time of 30 years, the expected static and dynamic loads and load history of the wing blades were estimated.

The conceptual design of the wingblade is a (load-bearing) tubular spar with aerodynamically shaped shells. The inner wing has a spar of steel while the outer wing has a D-shaped spar of glassfibre reinforced polyester; the shells are made of polyester with glassmats in a sandwich construction with a balsa core. The use of steel for the inner spar and glass-polyester for the outer spar is a trade-off between the requirement of low weight at large radius and available fabrication methods and dimensions for the glass-polyester spar. A preliminary design was used to evaluate static and dynamic stresses, deflections, and resonance frequencies of the wingblade, in particular the outer wing. This paper discusses only the design and materials of the outer wing, (Fig. 3 and 4).

The stresses in the outer wing originate from the aerodynamic loads, the centrifugal forces on the rotor and the forces caused by the fact that the wingblades are "tilted backwards" 6° from the rotor plane (the "cone angle force"). The important stresses are the flapwise bending stresses of the wing. The static stresses under extreme wind conditions (gale of 56 m/s, rotor stopped, flat side of wingblades facing into the wind) are from ca. 10 MN/m² near the wingtip to ca. 70 MN/m² at radius 8 m, referred to the spar-material; these stresses refer to the compressive side of the wingblades, slightly lower tensile stresses occur on the tension side of the wingblades. The dynamic stresses (in the spar-material) vary and are estimated to be ca. 35 ± 7 MN/m² for ca. 20 % of the operational time, ca. 21 ± 11 MN/m²

Fig. 1. The 630 kW windturbine on site.

Fig. 2. The twist of the outer wing, with sections of the airfoil at 1 m spacings, from radius 8 m to radius 20 m.

Fig. 3. The wingblade design.

Fig. 4. The cross section of the outer wing (radius 12 m) with materials specifications.

for ca. 40% of the time, and $6 \pm 6 \text{ MN/m}^2$ for ca. 40 % of the time. These stresses are compressive; the corresponding tensile stresses will be slightly less.

The deflection, in the flapwise mode, of the wingtip is ca. 1 m under extreme wind conditions.

The resonance frequency for a single outer wing (12 m length) during rotation is ca. 2.2 Hz; it is assumed that the outer wing is fixed at the strut support at radius 8 m. The three wingblades of the rotor will interact, and the important (lowest) resonance frequency of the rotor is 1.93 Hz. The imposed frequency due to rotation is three times the rotational frequency, i.e., $3 \times 0.557 = 1.67 \text{ Hz}$; the margin is thus ca. 15 %.

The materials specifications for the spar and shells of the outer wing were laid down on the basis of these performance data.

MATERIALS

The performance requirements lead to a spar material of high (bending) modulus, high static and dynamic strength and of low weight; the torsion modulus is not considered to be a critical material property. Glass fibre reinforced polyester was chosen, rather than e.g. carbon fibre reinforced epoxy, because it is a known material to the (Danish) manufacturing industry. The requirements to the materials properties and the geometrical parameters of the spar suggest a glass-polyester material of high volume fraction (>40 vol%) of glass fibres, and of highly oriented fibres, ideally parallel to the longitudinal axis of the spar.

An available and convenient technique for spar fabrication is (filament) winding of glass fibres onto a mandrel. Traditional filament winding with rovings allows fibre orientations of $20^\circ - 30^\circ$ at best, which is not acceptable in relation to the required stiffness, (elastic modulus).

A winding technique with the use of a woven glass tape was developed. The glass tape has about 90 % of the glass fibres (rovings) transverse to the length of the tape, with the remaining 10 % of glass forming lengthwise supporting rovings. Winding of this tape onto a mandrel produces a laminate with the 90 % fibres nearly parallel to the axis of the spar and the 10 % fibres nearly at 90° to the axis.

The spar is tapered only slightly from root to tip. The winding of a tape of finite width is assumed to occur as if the tape were wound onto a locally cylindrical mandrel. The equations for this winding are:

$$B = C \sin \theta$$

$$B = S \cos \theta$$

$$S = C \operatorname{tg} \theta$$

where the parameters are explained in Fig. 5; B is the effective width of the tape, S is the advancement of the tape per revolution, and C is the local circumference of the mandrel. The angle θ is the orientation of the 90 % of the fibres relative to the axis of the spar, and is also the angle at which the tape approaches the mandrel. The circumference varies from $C = 1.52 \text{ m}$ at the root (radius 8 m) to $C = 0.46 \text{ m}$ at the tip (radius 20 m). With an effective tape width of $B = 0.10 \text{ m}$, the required advancement at the root end of the mandrel is $S = 0.100217 \text{ m}$. For practical reasons the winding machine is operated with a constant $S = 0.100217 \text{ m}$, which means that the effective width of the tape decreases very slightly towards the tip of the mandrel ($B = 0.0979 \text{ m}$ at the tip). The angles θ of the fibre orientation for these operational parameters are calculated (Fig. 6) and it is seen that (the 90 % of) the fibres deviate only slightly (between 4° and 12°) from the spar-axis.

The tape winding is done from the root to the tip, and back from the tip to the root, etc. The stacking sequence for the laminate then becomes:

(+0, -(90-0)); (-0, +(90-0)); (+0, -(90-0)); (-0, +(90-0)); etc. where the first bracket indicates a double (woven) layer, wound from the root to the tip, with the 90 % fibres at $+\theta$ and the 10 % fibres at $-(90-\theta)$, and the second bracket refers to the

Fig. 5. Geometry of tape winding on a (cylindrical) mandrel; the sketch shows the developed surface of the mandrel.

tape feed arrangement
 Advancement per revolution
 $S = 0.100217 \text{ m}$

Fig. 6. Fibre orientation θ as function of position along the spar; the angle θ is also the angle of approach for the glass tape during winding.

Advancement per revolution
 $S = 0.100217 \text{ m}$
 Glass content $V_f = 0.50$
 $\frac{\text{Weight of glass of orientation } \theta}{\text{Weight of glass of orientation } 90 - \theta} = 14 : 1$

Fig. 7. Calculated stiffnesses of the glass-polyester material of the spar as function of position along the spar.

next double layer wound from the tip to the root, etc. On the basis of these fibre orientations and a total volume fraction of 50 %, the tensile modulus (E_x) and the shear modulus (G_{xy}) of the laminate was calculated as a function of position along the spar, see Fig. 7.

The cross section of the spar is D-shaped; this means that the tape during winding will pack less densely on the less curved parts and more densely on the sharply curved parts of the circumference. This results in, respectively, a locally lower and a locally higher than average volume fraction of fibres, which causes e.g. E_x and G_{xy} to vary along the circumference. Therefore all parameters refer to the "shoulder" positions on the spar (see Fig. 4).

The wall thickness of the spar was determined from the design calculation programme, based on the finite element method, and ranges from 24 mm at the root to 6 mm at the tip of the spar (referred to the "shoulder" position). The resulting flexural rigidity of the wing falls off, from root to tip, faster than linearly.

The requirements to the shell material are low weight, high bending stiffness and reasonable strength. These requirements are met by a sandwich material of polyester with glass mats and a balsa core. This material is well known to the industry, in particular to boat builders. The specifications (Fig. 4) comprise gelcoat (external surface), 1-2 mm glass-polyester, 10 - 16 mm balsa, and 1-2 mm glass-polyester (internal surface). Those parts of the shells, which enclose the spar, have no balsa core.

FABRICATION

The spars were fabricated on a (conventional) filament winding machine, which was modified for the tape winding technique. The mandrel, of shape equal to the internal shape of the spar, was made of a supporting steel tube, fitted with a skin of steel plates, that gives the outer D-shape. The mandrel was supported at its ends and driven by the machinery through the root end support bearing.

During tape winding the machine (Fig. 8) was operated with a constant advance-ment, $S = 0.100217$ m, of the tape feed arrangement along the mandrel; thus a constant ratio was maintained between the rotational speed of the mandrel and the linear movement of the tape feed arrangement, but the speed of winding could be varied. The glass tape, of weight 256 g/m^2 , was 0.21 m wide and was wound with nearly half overlap such that the effective width of the tape during winding was $B = 0.10$ m. Winding with half overlap causes a double layer of tape to be laid down during each travel along the mandrel.

Two important differences occur relative to (tape) winding onto a straight cylindrical mandrel:

1) The conical shape, which determines the fibre orientation θ , also governs the direction from which the tape must approach the mandrel, see Fig. 5. A mechanical arrangement was built to control the varying angle of the tape feed during the linear movement along the mandrel.

2) The conical shape and the finite width of the tape have the effect, that one side of the tape will always be tight around the mandrel while the other side of the tape will always be slack. It is necessary to take up this slack continuously in order to maintain the correct placing of the tape and the correct angle of fibre orientation. The take-up of the slack is done by inserting a wedge under the tape and withdrawing it after the next revolution. The correct feed of the tape onto the mandrel is controlled visually by the person who operates the wedge, (Fig. 9).

The glass tape is supplied with polyester by passing through a soaking apparatus mounted on the tape feed arrangement, (Fig. 10). The amount of polyester carried by the tape governs the volume fraction of glass in the laminate, and the soaking apparatus needs careful adjustment to ensure high volume fractions (>40 %).

Fig. 8. Tape winding of spar; the mandrel with some layers of glass tape is to the right, and the tape feed arrangement with roll of glass tape and soaking apparatus is to the left.

Fig. 9. (a) The wedge is inserted during tape winding. (b) Wedge arrangement.

Fig. 10. The glass tape in the soaking apparatus.

The required thickness of the laminate is built up during winding by varying the length of travel of the feed arrangement at each layer, the layers of short length are being placed early in the fabrication and the layers of full length at the end. The final thickness of the laminate at the root end comprises 96 single layers of glasstape, each layer contributing 0.25 mm. The typical weight of the 12 m spar is 365 kg and the net winding time was ca. 4 hours.

The shells for the wing are fabricated in the traditional way by hand lay-up in moulds, made from a complete model of the wing.

The assembling of the wing is made by adhesive bonding of the spar into the shells; the operation is done in two steps, the first step allows an inspection of the position of the spar inside the shells. The completed outer wing (including steel parts for the connection to the inner wing) weighs 910 kg.

FABRICATION CONTROL

The tape winding process was monitored in detail; the amount of glass fibres and the amount of polyester was recorded continuously, and this confirmed a uniform supply of raw materials to the mandrel, ensuring constant material composition throughout the spar (with the previously mentioned variations along the circumference). The viscosity of the polyester was measured regularly during fabrication and adjusted, if necessary, to a (not known) constant value by varying the styrene content of the polyester. A constant viscosity of the polyester proved beneficial in controlling the soaking of the glass tape, and thus ensuring a constant volume fraction of glass.

The fibre orientations were measured at regular intervals during fabrication, and were within $\pm 10^\circ$ of the axis of the spar, most of them probably within $\pm 5^\circ$, referring to the "longitudinal" fibres.

The thickness of the laminate was measured at regular intervals during fabrication, and the final thicknesses were in agreement with the nominal thicknesses.

MATERIALS TESTING

The fabricated spars were ca. 13 m long, leaving a 1 m length (radius 7 to 8 m) as control part. Samples were cut from the "shoulder" position of the upper (curved) side and of the lower (flat) side of the spar at radius ≈ 7.5 m.

The nominal thickness is 24 mm, but because of the variation of properties commensurate with the variation of thickness along the circumference, the actual thicknesses of all samples are recorded. Because the same amount of glass is present all along the circumference, the relation holds:

$$V_f \cdot t = \text{constant along circumference,}$$

where V_f is the local volume fraction of glass and t is the local thickness of spar-material.

The density was measured by the immersion method, and the weight fraction of glass was obtained by the ignition loss method (ASTM 2584). From these measurements the volume fraction of glass and the (volume) fraction of porosity were calculated.

Mechanical tests in tension were made on specimens with a gauge section of 200 mm x 25 mm x t (E-modulus) and a gauge section (machined on the same specimens) tapered from 25 mm at the ends to 15 mm at mid-length, (ultimate tensile strength and strain). The samples were held in specially made grips and tested at a nominal strain rate of $5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$ in an Instron 250 kN machine, (Fig. 11).

The elastic tensile modulus, the limit of proportionality in terms of stress and strain, and the ultimate tensile strength as well as an estimate of the ultimate

Fig. 11. Tensile testing of spar-material; the specimen exploded in less than 1/4 second.

tensile strain are listed in Table 2.

Spar no.	Spec. no.	Thick-ness mm	Density g/cm ³	Fibre vol. %	Porosity %	E GN/m ²	Limit of Proportion.		σ_{UTS} MN/m ²	ϵ_{UTS} %
							σ MN/m ²	ϵ %		
2	a	23.2	1.76	46.4	4.1	31.8	103	0.32	523	1.8
2	b	24.10	1.76	43.7	4.4	32.2	50	0.16	555	1.6
3	a	23.13	1.73	45.9	7.4	31.6	-	-	535	-
3	b	24.20	1.66	44.5	10.9	29.8	101	0.34	500	-
4	a	22.97	1.77	47.1	4.3	33.2	95	0.29	495	1.7
4	b	24.47	1.74	42.9	4.1	31.0	47	0.15	550	-
5	a	21.97	1.81	48.4	2.5	35.3	56	0.16	584	1.7
5	b	22.90	1.80	46.3	3.2	33.9	78	0.23	586	2.1
6	a	22.93	1.75	45.9	4.5	36.1	56	0.15	576	2.3
6	b	24.47	1.72	42.5	5.3	30.8	60	0.20	530	2.3
7	a	22.93	1.77	46.0	3.2	32.9	96	0.29	531	2.0
7	b	24.63	1.75	42.4	3.7	31.1	79	0.26	566	1.5

A total of 7 spars were fabricated.

Table 2

The values of the E-modulus are plotted versus the volume fractions (each corrected to the thickness of the actual tensile specimen), Fig. 12. The simple straight line from the law of mixtures for unidirectional composites is drawn as a reference, and we see that the laminates are rather close to this maximum-line.

The strain at the limit of proportionality is of the order 0.2-0.3%; this is close to values found in other glass reinforced polyester composites [1], and also close to values for the first detectable acoustic emission [1].

Fig. 12. The E-modulus of the spar-material versus the volume fraction of glass.

Fig. 13. Typical stress-strain curve of the spar-material.

The ultimate tensile strength is acceptable for the present application, but is probably affected by porosity. The ultimate tensile strain is difficult to define, because internal damage starts at lower loads and causes a jerky stress-strain curve, see Fig. 13.

The shell material contains about 20 vol% of glass, as is normal in hand lay-up work. Preliminary results from bending tests show a bending strength of ca. 180 MN/m² for the sandwich material.

COMPONENT TESTS

Component tests include elastic tests (stiffness), dynamic tests (resonance frequency), and failure tests (ultimate strength and strain). Tests were made on the outer 6 meter section of both the spar and the complete wing, on a 4 meter section of the wing (radius 8 to 12 m), and on the full length (12 m) spar and wing. The purpose was both to measure the actual wing performance and to compare the results with the performance calculated from the design programme.

The elastic deflection test for the complete 12 m wing showed reasonable agreement with the calculated flexural rigidity. A comparison with the 12 m spar gives an estimate of the fraction of a total (aerodynamic) load that (formally) is carried by the spar; this fraction is ca. 70%.

Measurements of the (lowest) resonance frequency of the 12 m spar and the 12 m wing gave values of 2.7 Hz and 2.18 Hz, respectively. The frequency of a rotating wing is ca. 5% higher than that of a stationary wing, due to centrifugal forces. The frequency of a (rotating) wing in the rotor is lower than that of an independent wing, due to coupling effects in the rotor. The Table 3 shows the relevant values:

	Status	Frequency (Hz)	
		Exp.	Calc.
1 wing	stationary, independent	2.18	2.12
1 wing	rotating, coupled	1.94	1.93

Table 3

The agreement is satisfactory, and it is further observed that the frequency (1.94) is ca. 16% above the rotationally imposed frequency of 1.67 Hz.

Tests in bending to final failure were made for the 6 m spar, for the 6 m wing, and for the 4 m section which includes the connection arrangement between the outer wing and the inner wing. Strain gauges were mounted on the test components at the position of the (expected) failure. The applied flapwise bending moments (at fracture) were calculated from the test arrangement. The results are listed in Table 4.

Test component	Position radius m	Measured failure strain, compressive %	Flapwise bending moment, M kNm	Strain, calc. from M, compressive %
6 m wing	16.1	0.75		
4 m section	9.5	0.56	520	0.6

Table 4

The failures were all in compression (on the curved side of the spar/wing), as expected. The strains are (perhaps) low values, caused by an imperfect laminate (the 6 m spar and wing were early experimental sections). The failure bending moment is ca. 2.6 times the (calculated) bending moment (at radius 9.5 m) during extreme wind conditions (gale of 56 m/s).

Dynamic tests (fatigue) have not been made, mainly due to a very tight time schedule. Strain gauges have been fitted to (one) wing and will be used to follow the strain history during service, thus producing information on the (real) fatigue history of the wings.

CONCLUSIONS

The fabricated spars and wings show the expected mechanical behaviour, and the materials and the design have met the requirements. In particular, it was possible to "design" the glass-polyester laminate for the spar such that the material properties are acceptable. It is not likely that the mechanical properties, e.g. the tensile modulus, can be increased further for the present materials combination (glass and polyester) and fabrication method (tape winding).

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REFERENCE

1. NORWOOD, L. S. and MILLMAN, A. F., Composites, vol 11, Jan. 1980, pp.39-45.